

varieties sown 15 May 1986. Tip drying was measured at 40 d after seeding. Ten plants were selected at

random for each entry (25-m² plots). Leaves and dried tips were counted (see table). □

Rice entries showing extent of tip drying. TNAU, India.

Rice entries with indicated % of leaf tip drying				
Up to 10%	11-20%	21-30%	31-40%	41-50%
TNAU801793	TNAU801790	IR56	TNAU801103	Co 41
TNAU831520	Rasi	TNAU83069/1	IR64	TPS 1
TNAU831521	PY3	ADT31	TKM9	
	TNAU83077	ASD16	IR50	
	PY2	MDUI	TNAU83134	
	TNAU842805	AD85003		
	ET1722	TM8089		
	TNAU842806	ADT36		
	ET4786	IR36		
	TNAU83133	IR60		
	Co 37			
	TNAU801803			
	TNAU830641			
	AD85001			
	TNAU801804			

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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization WEATHER

Factors causing winter yield declines in high-yielding varieties

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We studied the factors responsible for low productivity of high-yielding varieties grown Sep-Jun 1983-86. Treatments consisted of seven planting dates between 22 Aug and 12 Nov, of IR8, Jaya, IR20, and Bharathi. The layout was a split-plot design with three replications. Cultural practices and fertilizer applications were optimum. Weather variations were recorded.

Preliminary analysis for IR8 and Jaya are presented here. Yields varied from 1.0 to 4.6 t/ha for Jaya and 0.7 to 4.4 t/ha for IR8. This wide variation could not be attributed primarily to spikelet sterility (see table).

Correlation analysis between

Performance of two high-yielding varieties under different planting dates during three winter seasons in Kerala, India.

Planting date	Jaya				IR8			
	Height (cm)	Thousand spikelets per m ²	Thousand filled grains per m ²	Grain yield (t/ha)	Height (cm)	Thousand spikelets per m ²	Thousand filled grains per m ²	Grain yield (t/ha)
<i>1983-84</i>								
22 Aug	82	26.8	18.4	4.6	83	27.7	18.5	4.4
5 Sep	91	24.0	11.5	3.2	88	27.0	10.2	2.4
18 Sep	87	28.8	8.8	2.2	83	23.8	6.9	2.4
3 Oct	75	22.7	3.2	1.0	74	23.2	3.2	0.7
17 Oct	81	29.3	6.5	1.6	71	24.2	10.9	2.1
30 Oct	77	29.3	10.8	3.1	76	30.2	13.8	3.2
12 Nov	73	31.8	6.8	1.8	69	24.0	5.3	1.6
<i>1984-85</i>								
22 Aug	84	25.4	16.3	4.3	80	24.5	13.9	3.6
5 Sep	81	25.8	13.4	3.4	77	25.2	12.0	3.1
18 Sep	85	28.8	13.6	3.4	81	26.9	13.9	3.6
3 Oct	78	32.1	13.4	3.4	76	33.9	10.6	2.8
16 Oct	78	25.2	10.9	2.9	76	28.7	12.3	3.2
30 Oct	73	26.5	13.8	3.4	69	26.0	12.3	3.1
12 Nov	74	28.2	14.6	3.9	75	27.7	13.2	3.6
<i>1985-86</i>								
22 Aug	82	22.8	7.7	2.3	80	24.3	7.6	2.2
5 Sep	81	25.8	13.9	4.0	80	26.9	14.0	3.9
18 Sep	84	30.2	12.4	3.6	84	25.0	12.3	3.6
3 Oct	80	27.7	14.5	4.1	80	23.6	13.1	3.6
16 Oct	80	28.9	13.2	3.3	80	28.5	13.5	3.4
30 Oct	77	29.0	14.2	4.0	79	26.4	14.2	4.0
12 Nov	83	30.3	13.7	3.8	71	27.9	13.9	3.7

weather parameters and yield showed a positive relationship between total solar radiation during 5-15 d before 50% heading and a negative relationship between number of rainy days 15-30 d before 50% heading. Yield was predicted by these equations:

$$\text{Jaya: } Y = 11.74^{**}X_1 - 308.02^{**}X_2 - 2175$$

(3.91) (2.16)

$$R = 0.73$$

$$\text{IR8: } Y = 10.36^{**}X_1 - 238.80 X_2 - 1720$$

(3.42) (1.65)

$$R = 0.68$$

**Significant at 1% level
*Significant at 5% level

Where, Y = grain yield (kg/ha),
 X_1 = mean solar radiation 5-15 d before 50% heading in mWh/cm² per d, and

X_2 = number of rainy days 15-30 d before 50% heading.

Figures in parentheses are the "t" values of the regression coefficients.

Yield declines were more predominant for crops planted 18 Sep, 3 Oct, and 17 Oct, but yield reductions occurred under adverse weather parameters regardless of planting date. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization HYBRID RICE

Isolation of restorers and maintainers for two Chinese male-sterile lines having wild abortive (WA) cytoplasm

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Pollen from 26 early- and medium-duration rice varieties (8 from IRRI and 18 from India) were crossed with cyto-sterile Zhen Shan 97A and 12 varieties (6 from IRRI and 6 from India) were crossed with cyto-sterile Er-jiu Nan 1A to identify restorers and maintainers of pollen fertility. The two cyto-steriles are of Chinese origin with wild abortive (WA) cytoplasm.

The F_1 hybrids were raised during 1985 rabi in a test cross nursery at Paddy Breeding Station, TNAU. The

Pollen parents classified according to spikelet fertility percentage. TNAU, India.

Cytosterile	Effective restorers >80%	Weak restorers			Weak maintainers			Effective maintainers <5%
		60-80%	40-60%	20-40%	15-20%	10-15%	5-10%	
Zhen Shan 97A	-	-	IR36	IR54 IR56 IR58 IET1722 ASD8 TNAU658 K. Samba	IR40 IR50 IR52 IET4786 A09246 Co41	IR9752 TKM9 BAS370 PTB10 TNAU4372 Co 33 Co 37 Co 39	ADT31 PY2 Co 13 Kanchi	-
Er-jiu-Nan 1A	-	IET6208	IR9698 IET5103	IR19053 IR19058 IR9715 IET13267	IR18599	IR2307 AS19789 IET3630	BPHR5	-

main panicle of each hybrid plant was bagged and spikelet fertility was estimated at harvest. On the basis of spikelet fertility, pollen parents were classified as effective restorers (>80% spikelet fertility); partial or weak restorers (20 to 80% fertility), which is again subdivided into three groups;

weak maintainers (5-20%) and effective maintainers (<5%) (see table).

Stable male-sterile lines MS47A, MS37A, and MS31A are being developed utilizing weak maintainers Co 33, Co 37, and ADT31. A program to identify effective restorers and maintainers is in progress. □

Recurrent selection in rice

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To complement conventional breeding systems and to facilitate hybrid breeding programs, CNPAF and IRAT are synthesizing populations with broad genetic bases. The ability

of these populations to produce good varieties through conventional breeding or to provide good female parents with high prospects for cross pollination for the hybrid program will gradually increase through cyclic application of intermating and selection.

To facilitate intermating, a recessive male sterile gene [from IR36 male sterile (MS)] was introduced. Control of recombination and conservation of

the MS gene are assured by harvesting only open-pollinated seeds from male sterile segregants.

Two populations, one for irrigated rice and one for upland rice, are now ready to be used in conventional breeding systems. The rate of natural outcrossing on male sterile plants is sufficient to guarantee renovation of the populations. An average 165 seeds from male sterile plants of irrigated rice and 26 seeds from upland rice